

INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC AND PRACTICAL CONFERENCE

CONFERENCE DIRECTIONS

1. Scientific technologies
2. Economy
3. Finance
4. Mathematical analysis
5. Technical sciences
6. Pedagogy
7. Psychology
8. Philosophy
9. History
10. Informatics

INDEXING

Google Scholar

DOI:Zenodo

OpenAIRE|EXPLORE

MORE INFORMATION

www.bestjournalup.com

Google Scholar

OpenAIRE | EXPLORE

zenodo

DATE: December 15, 2024

Introduction

In the collection of materials of the conference, the role and role of Science, Education and production in the era of globalization, the pressing problems of the issues of interaction of these processes, feedback on their solutions were presented by mature specialists of the field.

In addition, research on the scientific and practical topic, carried out in the economics, Exact Sciences, Natural Sciences and socio-humanities during the globalization period, information is presented in the scientific and practical fields, which includes the latest innovative technologies in the fields of production.

It can be argued that this collection is one of the specific intersections of current thoughts and innovative ideas of the world of science. This scientific and practical conference was actively attended by professors and scientific researchers engaged in scientific research in Uzbekistan and foreign countries. In increasing the position of the scientific and practical conference, the professors and teachers of domestic and foreign higher educational institutions made a significant contribution.

Professors and teachers of foreign higher educational institutions who actively participated in the work of the conference made a worthy contribution to the high level of interaction with scientists of our country. The processes of international cooperation with foreign countries and exchange with them in the field of Science in the era of globalization have a positive effect on the development of Higher Education, the fields of Science and production. The materials of this conference are special in that they include a wide range of research, from theoretical developments to practical solutions, demonstrating the diversity of approaches and directions in this area.

In conclusion, it should be noted that this scientific and practical conference will be a very useful collection for everyone who is interested in modern research in the fields of further development of Higher Education, Science, Education and production in the era of globalization. The authors are responsible for the content and quality of the articles and abstracts included in the collection.

OILAVIY PSIXOLOG PSIXOTERAPEVTNING KASBIY YONDASHUVI

Salimova Farangiz Dilshod qizi

O'ZMU JF Psixologiya fakulteti Oila psixologiyasi yo'nalishi talabasi

Annotatsiya: Mazkur maqolamda oilaviy psixoterapevtning kasbiy yondashuvi, oilalar bilan ishlashda etika, estetika va kasbga doir ayrim metodik tafsiyalar yoritib o'tiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: *Kontseptual, uslubiy soha, kontseptsiya, paradigmasi, avtoritar uslub, integrativ, o'yin psixoterapiyasi, kommunikativ kompetentsiya, rekonstruktiv, trasfotmatsiya.*

Kirish. Hozirgi vaqtda oilaviy maslahat butun dunyo aholisi orasida eng mashhur psixologik yordam turi hisoblanadi. Turli yoshdagi odamlar nikohgacha bo'lgan davrdagi muammolarni hal qilish, oilaviy munosabatlar, ota-ona va bola munosabatlari, er (xotin)ning ota-onasi bilan muloqot, oila a'zolaridan birining shaxsiy muammolarini (masalan, turmush o'rtoqlar) va boshqalarni o'z ichiga oladi.

Shu munosabat bilan ushbu turdagi psixologik yordamning turli xil maqsadlarini ta'kidlash mumkin:

- oila, turmush, nikoh, otalik, onalik qadriyatlarini shakllantirish;
- disfunktsional rollarning o'zaro ta'sirini o'zgartirish, oila a'zolari tomonidan ijro etiladigan rollarning repertuarini kengaytirish;
- shaxslararo aloqani takomillashtirish, oila a'zolarining bir-biri bilan va tashqi dunyo bilan samarali o'zaro aloqalari;
- nizoli vaziyatlarning oldini olish qobiliyatini shakllantirish va rivojlantirish, agar ular paydo bo'lsa, ularni hal qilishning konstruktiv usullari;
- oilaning ishlashiga konstruktiv munosabatni shakllantirish, o'z hayoti, yaqinlari hayoti va umuman oilaviy hayot tuzilishi uchun mas'uliyat, hayotiy faoliyatni rivojlantirish;
- har bir oila a'zosi uchun shaxsiy o'sish imkoniyatini ta'minlash;
- qiyin hayotiy vaziyatni tushunish va qabul qilishda yordam berish (azoblanishni istisno qilmasdan), undan ijobiy chiqish yo'llarini izlash, o'ziga ishonish va o'z kelajagini rejalashtirish.

Asosiy qism. Kasbshunoslikning asosiy konseptual bosh tushunchasi bu kasb tushunchasidir. Kasbshunoslik adabiyotlarida kasb tushunchasining tavsifi juda ko'p. Avvalambor bu maxsus tayyorgarlikni talab etuvchi, inson doim tajribadan o'tkazuvchi va unga yashash uchun manba bo'lib xizmat qiluvchi mashg'ulotdir. Kasb bir xil faoliyat bilan shug'ullanuvchi kishilarni birlashtiradi. Bu faoliyat ichida ma'lum aloqalar va axloq normalari o'rnatiladi. Kasb jamiyatning mexnatga layoqatli a'zolarini ijtimoiy tashkillashtirishning aloxida shakli bo'lib, bunda a'zolar

faoliyatining umumiy turi va kasbiy ongi bilan birlashgan. Xalqimizda maqol bor “Hunarli o‘zar hunarsiz to‘zar”.

Kasb bo‘yicha tafovutlar

1-jadval.

Psixolog	Klinik psixolog	Psixoterapevt	Psixiatr
Psixologiya darajasiga ega bo‘lgan shaxs. Uning qo‘lida bakalavr yoki magistr darajasi bor, bu insonning psixolog bo‘lishi mumkinligini isbotlaydi. Va allaqachon asosiy ta‘lim mavjud bo‘lganda, uni sertifikatlar, kurslar, treninglar bilan oshirish mumkin. Eng muhimi, psixolog qila olmaydi: tashxis qo‘yish, davolanishni buyurish.	Bu shifokor emas, lekin u psixologiya va tibbiyot chorrahasida ishlaydi. Uning vazifasi kasalliklarga chalingan odamlarga hamroh bo‘lishdir, bu kasallik ruhiy zulmni keltirib chiqaradi. O‘lim qo‘rquvi, vahima hujumlari, tashvish. Klinik psixolog davolanishni buyurmaydi, lekin qo‘rquv va tashvishlarni engishga yordam beradi.	Tayanch oliy tibbiy ta‘lim oladi, so‘ngra ixtisoslashtirilgan ordinaturadan o‘tadi. Ya‘ni, u ma‘lum belgilarga ega bo‘lgan odam bilan nima qilish kerakligini biladi, kompleks tarzda harakat qiladi va dori-darmonlarni buyurishi mumkin. Uning aralashuvi kasallikning rivojlanishiga to‘sqinlik qilishi mumkin.	“Psixiatriya” mutaxassisligi bo‘yicha tibbiy ta‘lim olgan shaxs. Shuningdek, u dori-darmonlarni buyurish huquqiga ega. Tashxis qo‘yilgan aniq bemorlar bilan normadan tashqariga chiqadigan holatlar bilan ishlashga qodir. Ular aytganidek: psixiatrning ustidan kulgandan ko‘ra, psixologga yig‘lash yaxshiroqdir.

Psixoterapiyada yondashuvlar va yo‘nalishlar mavjud. Psixoterapiyadagi yondashuvlar avtomobilning markasi va yo‘nalishlar - tana turlari. Ya‘ni, yondashuv umuman inson psixikasi qanday ishlashini tushuntiradi va yo‘nalish psixologga ishlash uchun vositalarni beradi. Har bir inson yondashuvlarni eshitgan va ularning farqlari:

Psixoanaliz. Inson ongida bostirilgan instinktlar o‘rtasida uzluksiz kurash borligini ta‘kidlaydi. Inson ongida sodir bo‘layotgan voqealar esa bu kurashning natijasidir.

Bixeviorizm. Inson stimullar va reaksiyalar tizimida. Rag‘batlantirish tashqi, lekin ichki ham bor. Ularni tushunib, siz ichki holatni va tashqi xatti-harakatlarni tuzatishingiz mumkin.

Gumanistik yondashu. Inson jamiyat talablari va ichki “men shunday his qilaman” o‘rtasida ziddiyatga ega. Gap shundaki, bu ikki tomonni iloji boricha uyg‘unlashtirish.

Xulosa. Oilaviy hayot bilimlari, ko‘nikmalari va odatlarini shakllantirishda oilaning o‘rni beqiyosdir. Psixoterapevtik maktabdan qat’iy nazar, oilaviy terapevt, birinchidan, oila a‘zolari bilan terapevtik munosabatlarni o‘rnatish va qo‘llab-quvvatlash, ikkinchidan, mijozning holatini va uning oila tizimini tahlil qila olishi, uchinchidan, harakat qila olishi kerak, ya‘ni rivojlanish va o‘zgarishlar uchun sharoit yaratish uchun ongli aralashuv orqali.

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar:

1. D.T.Ismatova. Oila psixoterapiyasi nazariyasi. Vuxoro-2021.
2. V.Karimova. Oila psixologiyasi. T-2008.
3. Баркер Ф. Использование метафор в психотерапии НПО «Модек», Воронеж, 1995 г.
4. Браун Дж., Кристенсен Д. Теория и практика семейной психотерапии. С.-Пб., «Питер», 2001 г.
5. Варга А.Я. Семейная психотерапия. С.-Пб., «Речь», 2001 г.